

Dear participant,

Thank you for agreeing to take part in our meeting. Your participation will help us develop our research and we may be able to help more people recover from type 2 diabetes.

We are looking to develop a research study comparing between two types of diet:

- 1) A low-Calorie diet consisting of soups and shakes only
- 2) A low-Calorie food-based diet that consists of foods given in small amounts.

To explain what each of the diets means, you will find examples of both types of diet in your pack. Both these diets may help people with type 2 diabetes stop taking medications and recover from diabetes. We would like to ask you your opinion on whether you think these diets are acceptable to you. We will also ask your opinion on a questionnaire and the use of devices to measure your physical activity and your sleep quality. You will have the opportunity to tell us how we could help you and your community be more involved in diabetes research.

We will ask you to take part in a virtual or face-to-face meeting to discuss this. We will ask you if we can record the meeting and we will comply with the privacy policy of Manchester Metropolitan University. If you agree for the meeting to be recorded, we confirm that we will delete the recorded video by 30 November 2021.

As a thank you, we will give you a voucher of £20 for your participation.

We look forward to joining our meeting. If you have further queries, please do not hesitate to contact me.

Low-Calorie diets for treating diabetes

Option 1: Soups and shakes diet:

People who take part in the diabetes research study will be asked to consume a diet only consisting of soups and shakes for 12 weeks. Food will be reintroduced after then. Here is an example of soups and shakes diets for one day (850 Kcal).

A one-day plan looks approximately like this:

Here are the choices of soups you have:

Chicken and Mushroom flavour:

Maltodextrin, Skimmed milk powder, Soya flour, Milk protein, Soya protein isolate, Inulin, Flavouring, Soya lecithin, Potassium chloride, Hydrolysed maize protein, Monocalcium phosphate, Compound vitamin and mineral mixture[†], Dried mushrooms, Stabiliser: xanthan gum, Onion powder, Dried parsley, Malt extract, Tricalcium phosphate, Black pepper. Allergens: Contains milk, soya, egg, barley and wheat.

Oriental Chilli flavour:

Maltodextrin, Soya flour, Skimmed milk powder, Milk protein, Soya protein isolate, Inulin, Textured soya protein, Flavouring, Potassium chloride, Soya lecithin, Hydrolysed maize protein, Monocalcium phosphate, Dried red peppers, Dried mushrooms, Compound vitamin and mineral mixture[†], Stabiliser: xanthan gum, Onion powder, Salt, Garlic powder, Tricalcium phosphate, Dried coriander, Black pepper, Colour: beta-carotene. Allergens: Contains milk, soya and wheat.

Spicy Tomato flavour (with sweeteners):

Whey protein, Tomato powder, Maltodextrin, Inulin, Refined soya oil, Soya protein isolate, Potassium chloride, Monocalcium phosphate, Salt, Hydrolysed maize protein, Flavouring, Citric acid, Compound vitamin and mineral mixture[†], Calcium carbonate, Stabiliser: xanthan gum, Dried parsley, Soya lecithin, Sweeteners (acesulfame K, aspartame*), Colours (paprika extract, beta-carotene). *Contains source of phenylalanine. Allergens: Contains milk and soya.

Vegetable flavour:

Maltodextrin, Soya protein isolate, Soya flour, Milk protein, Inulin, Hydrolysed maize protein, Dried vegetables, Soya lecithin, Flavouring, Dipotassium phosphate, Potassium chloride, Calcium carbonate, Compound vitamin and mineral mixture[†], Stabiliser: xanthan gum, Monocalcium phosphate, Black pepper, Dried parsley, Colour: beta carotene. Allergens: Contains milk, soya and wheat.

†Compound vitamin and mineral mixture:

Magnesium oxide, Ascorbic acid, Ferrous fumarate, Nicotinamide, Copper gluconate, Zinc oxide, Vitamin E acetate, Manganese sulphate, Calcium D-pantothenate, Pyridoxine hydrochloride, Thiamin hydrochloride, Riboflavin, Vitamin A acetate, Sodium molybdate, Chromic chloride, Folic acid, Sodium selenite, Potassium iodate, D-biotin, Vitamin K, Vitamin D3, Vitamin B12. Important allergen information: All soups have been produced in a factory that handles nuts and peanuts.

Here are the choices of shakes you have:

Banana flavour (with sweetener):

Skimmed milk powder, Soya flour, Soya protein isolate, Inulin, Compound vitamin and mineral mixture[†], Soya lecithin, Potassium chloride, Flavouring, Stabilisers (xanthan gum, carrageenan), Sweetener: aspartame*, Colour: beta-carotene.

*Contains source of phenylalanine.

Allergens: Contains milk and soya.

Butterscotch flavour (with sweetener):

Skimmed milk powder, Soya flour, Soya protein isolate, Inulin, Compound vitamin and mineral mixture[†], Soya lecithin, Potassium chloride, Flavouring, Stabilisers (xanthan gum, carrageenan), Malt extract, Sweetener: aspartame*, Colour: beta-carotene.

*Contains source of phenylalanine.

Allergens: Contains milk, soya and barley.

Chocolate flavour (with sweetener):

Skimmed milk powder, Soya flour, Soya protein isolate, Reduced fat cocoa powder, Compound vitamin and mineral mixture[†], Soya lecithin, Inulin, Potassium chloride, Stabilisers (xanthan gum, carrageenan), Flavouring, Sweetener: aspartame*.

* Contains source of phenylalanine.

Allergens: Contains milk and soya.

Chocolate Mint flavour (with sweetener):

Skimmed milk powder, Soya flour, Soya protein isolate, Reduced fat cocoa powder, Compound vitamin and mineral mixture[†], Soya lecithin, Inulin, Flavouring, Potassium chloride, Stabilisers (xanthan gum, carrageenan), Dipotassium phosphate, Sweetener: aspartame*.

* Contains source of phenylalanine.

Allergens: Contains milk and soya.

Fruits of the Forest flavour (with sweetener):

Skimmed milk powder, Soya protein isolate, Soya flour, Inulin, Soya lecithin, Compound vitamin and mineral mixture[†], Potassium chloride, Colours (beetroot powder, anthocyanin), Stabilisers (xanthan gum, carrageenan), Flavouring, Sweetener: aspartame*.

* Contains source of phenylalanine.

Allergens: Contains milk and soya.

Strawberry flavour (with sweetener):

Skimmed milk powder, Soya protein isolate, Soya flour, Inulin, Soya lecithin, Compound vitamin and mineral mixture[†], Potassium chloride, Flavouring, Stabilisers (xanthan gum, carrageenan), Colour: beetroot powder, Sweetener: aspartame*.

* Contains source of phenylalanine.

Allergens: Contains milk and soya.

Toffee & Walnut flavour (with sweetener):

Skimmed milk powder, Soya flour, Soya protein isolate, Inulin, Compound vitamin and mineral mixture[†], Soya lecithin, Potassium chloride, Stabilisers (xanthan gum, carrageenan), Flavouring, Sweetener: aspartame*.

* Contains source of phenylalanine.

Allergens: Contains milk and soya.

Vanilla flavour (with sweetener):

Skimmed milk powder, Soya flour, Soya protein isolate, Inulin, Compound vitamin and mineral mixture[†], Soya lecithin, Potassium chloride, Stabilisers (xanthan gum, carrageenan), Flavouring, Sweetener: aspartame*.

* Contains source of phenylalanine.

Allergens: Contains milk and soya.

†Compound vitamin and mineral mixture:

Sodium citrate, Magnesium oxide, Ascorbic acid, Ferrous fumarate, Nicotinamide, Copper gluconate, Zinc oxide, Vitamin E acetate, Manganese sulphate, Calcium D-pantothenate, Pyridoxine hydrochloride, Thiamin hydrochloride, Riboflavin, Vitamin A acetate, Sodium molybdate, Chromic chloride, Folic acid, Sodium selenite, Potassium iodate, D-biotin, Vitamin K, Vitamin D3.

Important allergen information: All shakes have been produced in a factory that handles nuts and peanuts.

Option 2: food-based diet

People who take part in the diabetes research study will be asked to consume a low-Calorie diet for 12 weeks. The diet has been tailored to include components of the Mediterranean diet; this diet had many health benefits in the past for preventing diabetes and its complications. You will have more foods after 12 weeks. Here is an example of a few days of meal plans:

(you will have more day options during your study)! If you are vegan or vegetarian, you will have the right options for you).

Day 1:

Morning:

Breakfast 200g of low-fat yogurt topped with 2 tablespoons of berries (30g)

Snack Handful of raw almonds (23g)

Lunch Tuna salad (100g of drained tuna with 3 cups of mixed salad leaves, one medium tomato, one large cucumber and 1 tbsp of olive oil).

Dinner Lentil and carrot soup (80g dried red lentils, 1 medium onion, 2 medium carrots, 1tsp of olive oil)

1 medium apple

Day 2:

Breakfast Wholemeal thin toast (23g) with one medium soft-boiled egg

1 medium banana

Lunch Small chicken breast roasted (100g) with salad (3 cups of mixed salad leaves, one medium tomato, one large cucumber and 1 tbsp of olive oil)

Half cup of boiled brown rice (100g)

Dinner Reduced fat hummus (3tbsp) with dipping vegetables (2 medium carrots, 1 medium pepper)

Wholemeal thin toast (23g)

(853Kcal, 23g of Fat, 106g of CHO, 58g of protein)

Day 3

Breakfast Reduced fat cottage cheese (51g) with wholemeal thin toast (23g)

Vegetables (lettuce, medium tomato, large cucumber)

Snack Natural fat free yogurt (200g) with wholemeal crackers (10g)

Lunch lentil and carrot soup (80g dried red lentils, 1 medium onion, 2 medium carrots, 1tsp of olive oil)

1 medium fruit

Dinner: Omelette (2 eggs, 1 tsp of olive oil, 1 spring onion, 60g of baby spinach, ½ red or yellow pepper, 1 small, boiled potato (150g), ½ teaspoon dried oregano)

Quality of Life questionnaire:

EuroQoL5 EQ-5D-3L is a questionnaire that looks at the quality of life and if it will change during the study. We will ask people to fill it at the beginning and end of the study. Here is an example of it below. We will ask your opinion of this questionnaire during the meeting.

By placing a tick in one box in each group below, please indicate which statements best describe your own health state today.

Mobility

- I have no problems in walking about
- I have some problems in walking about
- I am confined to bed

Self-Care

- I have no problems with self-care
- I have some problems washing or dressing myself
- I am unable to wash or dress myself

Usual Activities *(e.g. work, study, housework, family or leisure activities)*

- I have no problems with performing my usual activities
- I have some problems with performing my usual activities
- I am unable to perform my usual activities

Pain / Discomfort

- I have no pain or discomfort
- I have moderate pain or discomfort
- I have extreme pain or discomfort

Anxiety / Depression

- I am not anxious or depressed
- I am moderately anxious or depressed
- I am extremely anxious or depressed

To help people say how good or bad a health state is, we have drawn a scale (rather like a thermometer) on which the best state you can imagine is marked 100 and the worst state you can imagine is marked 0.

We would like you to indicate on this scale how good or bad your own health is today, in your opinion. Please do this by drawing a line from the box below to whichever point on the scale indicates how good or bad your health state is today.

Your own health state today

(This questionnaire is available at <https://euroqol.org/eq-5d-instruments/eq-5d-3l-about/>)